

OPPORTUNITIES FOR E-COMMERCE DEVELOPMENT IN THE DIGITAL ECONOMY

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Abstract: This article presents opinions on the role and importance of e-commerce in the digital economy of our country, the stages of its development and opportunities for further development. An assessment of its capabilities and determination of development prospects are also highlighted.

Key words. Digital economy, marketing, e-commerce, electronic market.

Introduction. In connection with our country's entry into a new economic stage, large-scale work was carried out in all areas. As a result of the development of information technology, the e-commerce system has reached a new level. In Decree No. PF-6079 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M.Mirziyoyev dated October 5, 2020 “On approval of the strategy “Digital Uzbekistan - 2030” and measures for its effective implementation” “Electronic commerce and In order to develop the electronic payment system, the following activities are being carried out : development of remote banking services through the introduction of information and communication technologies, including remote customer identification systems; improve and update the legal framework for the development of e-commerce, as well as existing standards and regulations of e-commerce in order to comply with international e-commerce standards and modern information security requirements; development of digital infrastructure, increasing the volume and scale of connection to e-commerce platforms from personal digital equipment by further increasing the coverage and speed of the global information

network of mobile and wired Internet, etc.

Literature review. Therefore, in our country, until 2030, the tasks have been set to accelerate the implementation of digital transformation processes in all areas and thereby strengthen the country's economic power and take its rightful place in the world community. In this regard, let us clarify the concept of e-commerce.

Electronic commerce (e-commerce, visual “electronic commerce”) is the organization of trading practices via the Internet. An example of e-commerce is eBay, the largest online auction and store. To date, e-commerce has made a large-scale contribution to the economy of Uzbekistan, and the ground has been created for studying the current situation, problems and prospects in the country.

To achieve the desired development and prosperity of the global community, the need for information technology (IT) is growing rapidly. Enhanced economic growth and improved living standards of the planet's population are also the result of the penetration of information technology into our daily lives. World experience shows that ensuring the free flow of information accelerates the transition to a market economy and creates the basis for improving social well-being.

Analysis and results. The rapid development of information technology has not been without reflection in the economy. Today, the basis of achievements in the economy, especially in the field of modern marketing, lies in the highly developed and effective use of various segments of information technology. The economy of Uzbekistan is, of course, no exception. As a clear example, we can cite a number of segments of information technology, such as data networks, Internet information resources and electronic document flow between them, Internet marketing systems, business and commerce. For Uzbekistan, the development of information technology is of great importance in ensuring new economic ties. But this process occurs only if there is a certain level of information readiness of society, which arises as a result of raising educational standards in the field of information technology, modernizing national telecommunication networks, and forming a legal framework.

As a result of the gradual development of the economy of Uzbekistan, the importance of new principles of doing business, especially **e-commerce**, has increased. Today, every Internet user has tried to understand the meaning of the word e-commerce. On average, 1.5-2 trillion per year in the US markets are associated

with activities that have not yet had time to build their long history. Funds are transferred in US dollars.

The term "electronic commerce" includes technologies such as EDI (electronic data interchange), email, Internet, intranet (exchange of information within a company) and extranet (exchange of information with the outside world). In turn, the e-commerce system can be divided into three classes:

- Organization of retail trade (business-to-consumer, B2C);
- Establishing relationships with a business partner (business-to-business, B2B);
- Trade between consumers (consumer-to-consumer, C2C).

As e-commerce began to increase the range of goods and services every day, it brought together individuals, businesses, industries, government agencies and, finally, countries into one community, and the interaction of partners made it possible to achieve effective and barrier-free agreements. using information and telecommunication technologies.

E-commerce itself is divided into two types: tangible and intangible flows associated with the streaming service: intangible flows are intangible goods (software, construction projects, etc.), direct network transmission, direct network execution of tangible services (transport tickets, booking hotel rooms, etc.), partners (clients, customers, suppliers, givers, financial reports with subcontractors, banks, etc., information and telecommunications support for the provision of material services.

Such flows constitute a significant, and sometimes a very large part of the total flows as a result of one or another virtual business activity. Naturally, the use of power tools when servicing intangible flows leads to the acceleration of work processes and, as a result, to the development of e-commerce.

E-commerce has its own conveniences and advantages:

- The speed of obtaining information in international operations will increase;
- The period of production and sales is reduced;
- The costs of information exchange are reduced through the use of cheap communication means.

Establishing open relationships with consumers through the effective use of corporate information technologies, providing partners and clients with up-to-date information about goods and services, alternative sales methods, for example, electronic stores on commercial platforms, allows you to discover and create.

On the basis of e-commerce, new trading enterprises are being created - electronic stores; due to great competition, new types of services and goods appear in them. The main element of e-commerce is the sale and circulation of goods on the Internet. The circulation of goods must be carried out on the basis of comprehensive activities for its sale. This is the development and use of information, advertising activities and similar activities.

Today, the government authorities of Uzbekistan, when developing e-commerce, are guided by the following principles, which are widely used in world experience.

- The corporate sector should play an active role in the development of e-commerce;
- Government authorities should not be allowed to introduce various unreasonable restrictions on e-commerce;
- Government bodies can intervene in the process of e-commerce in order to support entities in this area and improve the legal framework;
- When developing measures to manage e-commerce, the government should take into account the characteristics of the Internet;
- The e-commerce process must occur on a global scale, regardless of administrative divisions and state borders.

It should be emphasized that along with the development of e-commerce in Uzbekistan, there are also a number of problems that impede the improvement of this sector. A quick and clear solution to these problems is one of the important requirements of our time. Because in the world experience, the following problems are widespread and awaiting solution, and as a result of their improper solution, serious crises may arise in this area.

Firstly, the necessary infrastructure is not yet sufficiently developed. Here are some examples:

- The number of providers directly connected to the global Internet is limited, as a result of which the Internet is delivered to customers through

transport from one provider to another, which is known to negatively affect the quality of service' secret shows.

➤ quality indicators of Internet services provided in the regions are significantly worse compared to the situation in the capital. As a result of not creating sufficient conditions for a dedicated connection (ADCL modem), clients use a direct dial-up connection. This, in turn, leads to insufficient quality of service.

Secondly, the number of Internet users is such that this situation does not allow the creation of a large market necessary for e-commerce (the number of Internet users in Uzbekistan is more than 2.5 million).

Thirdly, the lack of development of a reliable system providing online payments from bank account numbers of individuals. We can make payments with plastic cards issued by our banks only using special terminals, and according to international experience - with plastic cards, through special modules installed to accept payments directly online. Payment can also be made in the mines.

The main problem is that the online banking service for individuals has not become widespread in Uzbekistan. Internet banking allows bank customers to manage their accounts and make payments via the Internet or mobile phone. SMS banking, offered by several banks, is one-way and is intended only for obtaining account information and transaction history. This situation is one of the biggest obstacles to the development of e-commerce.

Fourthly, there is a lack of sufficient level of professionalism in the activities of existing online stores. According to the Communications and Information Agency, as of January 1, 2008, there were 24 online stores operating in Uzbekistan.

We propose the following as the main areas of attention in solving the above problems:

- It is necessary to deepen scientific research in the field of e-commerce. Scientific work, writing articles, creating specialized Internet resources, organizing regular forums and conferences, taking into account not only technical, but also economic and legal features of e-commerce when training personnel, prevents one of the main problems - the lack of qualified personnel.

- Development of competition in the field of telecommunications services. This leads to improved service quality, lower prices and the creation of a specific online audience for e-commerce.

- Ensuring the continued availability of favorable legal conditions for investment in the ICT sector in the prescribed manner.

- Creation of systems of self-government and exchange of experience.

- Development of an electronic education system

- Ensure widespread dissemination of information technologies throughout Uzbekistan. The introduction of information technologies not only in regional centers, but also in remote villages will lead to a significant increase in the volume of e-commerce.

- Effective implementation of the online banking system throughout the country. This will increase the ability of entrepreneurs engaged in wholesale and retail trade to freely trade their goods and services via the Internet. At the same time, this will lead to significant changes in other areas of the banking industry.

It can be easily noted that Uzbekistan, with its high intellectual capabilities, should not be left behind in the civilization of information technology.

The development of e-commerce will give our society the following results:

- The development of e-commerce has a positive effect on the structure of the labor market in Uzbekistan. The industrialization of high information technologies will create thousands of new jobs.

- Stabilizing the economy of Uzbekistan, increasing the competitiveness of goods and services, and developing e-commerce will lead to an increase in our export opportunities.

- E-commerce ensures an increase in the standard of living of the population and the development of such areas as marketing and management.

Conclusion. Thus, it should be emphasized that the opportunities for the development of e-commerce in Uzbekistan are growing every year. Its development creates opportunities for our national manufacturers to open new markets and find new customers. Following the chosen and current path of development of e-commerce will allow the economy of Uzbekistan to become one of the leading representatives of the world market in the future. Choosing the right way to solve the problems of e-commerce in Uzbekistan affects the well-being of the people, the progress of our society and our economic development.

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